

Distributive Numerals in Buginese Language: Morfo syntax Analysis

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ABSTRACT : This study aims to explain the behavior of distributive numeral morfo syntax in Buginese Language (BL) based on morfo syntactic behavior. This research is descriptive qualitative. Data were obtained from: (1) daily BL discussion by native speakers, (2) BL-literary texts, and (3) BL oral literature books. Data collection is done through fishing techniques by accompanying the language informant to speak, which aims to find data in the form of numerals in BL. The samples taken are five phrases or sentences in BL which contain the word numerals, which is taken purposively (according to the needs of the analysis). Data were analyzed using structural grammar methods. The results of the study show that based on morphological behavior, BL distributive numerals can be formed by using the ta(G)- prefix - on basic numerals. Prefix ta(G)- this can be accompanied by a suffix that states ownership and can also be in the form of reduplication. In addition, BL distributive numerals can also be explicitly expressed as lexical 'every' and at 'each '. This word can also experience a morphological process, which is to add a prefix to a mattungkek'each' and a sipattungkek'alone'. Furthermore, the words can also becomes reduplication to be: tungkek-tungkek 'each'. Syntactically, tungkek words always precede the numerical and noun word categories and cannot stand alone, whereas the padaword can stand alone in front of verb and adjective words, and do not experience the morphological process as well as the wordstungkek.

KEYWORDS - distributive numerals, morphological behavior, syntactic behavior

I. INTRODUCTION

The Buginese language (BL) is one of the Austronesian language families used by the Buginese ethnic group in South Sulawesi as an internal tribal communication. This language is the regional language which has the largest use in South Sulawesi Province. The Buginese language consists of several dialects, such as the Pinrang dialect which is similar to the Sidrap dialect, Bone dialect, Soppeng dialect, Wajo dialect, Barru dialect, Sinjai dialect, and so on.

BL numerals is very interesting to look at because it has a distinctive morphosyntactic behavior, which can change the category and identity of the word, in addition to its influence on changes in the meaning of words. In this paper the attention is directed to the behavior of distributive numeral morphosyntax of BL. The problems faced are (1) how the morphological behavior of the distributive numerals, and (2) how does the syntactic behavior. The results of this discussion will make a scientific contribution to the development of BL linguistics, especially the field of grammar. From here it will also reveal the sociological characteristics of Buginese society as a highly civilized society.

Departing from this phenomenon, the problem statement is proposed as follows: How are the morphological processes of Buginese distributive numerals? Based on the problem statement, the objective of this study then was to find Formulate construction patterns of Buginese language, which distribute the numerals at the at the clause / sentence level. The results of this study are expected to provide the following benefits. a.

can be used as a source of teaching materials for BL local content subjects in elementary and secondary schools, even universities; b. Practically, the results of this research can also be used as an effort to revitalize the BL so that it is prevented from language extinction.

Literature Review

The numeral words can be defined as a word used to indicate the exact number of an object. So, it can be asserted that numerals is a word or group of words used to express numbers or numbers (Hammarström in Klamer, 2017). Judging from the morphological type, the numeral system consists of two forms, namely (1) simple numerals and (2) complex numerals. Simple numerals are a form of numerals which are monomorphes, whereas numerals complex is a combination of simple numerals into a more complex form of numerals.

Distributive numerals

According to Champollion (2010), the terms of distributivity and derivative are widespread in semantic literature, but no standard definition is found. A number of related concepts can be distinguished in what word is used. The distributive, terms can be seen as a property of quantifiers, relationships between two constituents, predicate properties, or syntactic construction properties. Distributivity can also be enforced by using quantitative noun phrases headed by determinants such as each or each in Indonesian. In BL there is a defining word which states the distributive meaning, i.e. the 'every', then the reduplication form is *tungkek-tungkek* 'each'. However, it is typical in BL distributive meaning which can be expressed by pre morphological prefixes *ta(G)-*, both with or without reduplication and affixation.

Morphological Behavior

Affixation

Affixation is the process of adding a certain affix to the basic morpheme. In this connection there are three terms or concepts that have similarities, namely (a) affix, (b) *klitika*, and (c) *prolexeme*. *Klitika* or *klitik* is a free morpheme, but phonologically it is bound to other words or phrases. *Klitika* is usually spelled like an affix, but classically the word is at the phrase level. In BL there are examples of *ku-*, *mu-*, *-nya* (my book, your book, her book, each one is commensurate with its construction: my book, your book, her book). *Prolexeme* is a form of language which has a lexical meaning as well as a word, but cannot stand alone if it is not combined with other languages, and cannot be affixed, for example in Indonesian *chess-*, *dasa-*, *maha-* (quarter 'four months', *dasasila* 'ten basics', student).

Reduplication

According to Zamzani (1993), reduplication is a process and the result of repeating language units as a phonological or grammatical tool, so that in essence there can be found phonological reduplication and grammatical reduplication, with the meaning of grammatical reduplication including morphemic reduplication or morphological reduplication, and syntactic reduplication. Based on this definition, reduplication is further divided into four types, namely complete reduplication, voice copy reduplication, partial reduplication, and reduplication accompanied by affixing.

Composition

Composition (compounding) is the process of forming words by combining morphemes with words, or words with words that give rise to a new, special meaning (Moeliono ed., 1988). According to Ramlan (1985), the characteristics of compound words are as follows:

- (1) one or all of the elements are in the form of the main word;
- (2) it is impossible for the elements to be separated or altered in structure;
- (3) one or all of the elements are unique morphemes.

Inflection and derivation

According to Katamba, (1994) the difference in concept between inflectional and derivational is that inflectional is related to syntactic rules that can be predicted (predictable), automatic (automatic), systemic, fixed / consistent, and does not change lexical identity; For example the phonological behavior of -s may be predictable, but the meaning it generates may not. As for derivational, it tends to be unpredictable based on syntactic rules, is not automatic, not systematic, thus it is optional and changes the lexical identity.

Morphophonemic principles

According to Kamsinah (2017), morphophonemic is meant as a subsystem that is related to phoneme changes due to the meeting between one morpheme and another morpheme. It is said that the meeting of morphemes in word formation, both in Indonesian and in English, has its own uniqueness.

II. RESEARCH METHOD

This research is a qualitative descriptive study, which is a study that describes the behavior of numeral morphosyntax of attributable BL as is. Data for analysis were obtained from: (1) daily BL discussion by native speakers, (2) BL-accented texts, and (3) open BL oral literature. Data collection is done through fishing techniques by accompanying language informants speaking by aiming to find data in the form of distributive numerals in BL. The samples taken are as many as three canoes with five phrases or sentences in BL which contain the word distributive numerals, which is taken purposively (according to the needs of the analysis). Data were analyzed using structural grammar methods.

The population of this study is all grammatical constructions that contain BL distributive numerals, both those that behave morphologically and that behave syntactically. The sample of this study are three to five phrases or sentences in BL which contain the word numerals, which are taken from the everyday BL formulations and BL manuscripts (according to the needs of the analysis).

III. DISCUSSION

Distributive Numeral Morphological Behavior of Bugineselanguagcan be formed by the use of the prefix *ta(G)* - on basic numerals. Prefix *ta(G)*- this can also be accompanied by a suffix which states ownership, in this case possessive *-ku* (first person singular), *-ta* (plural first people), *-mu* (second person singular, and *-na* (third person singular) In addition, the prefix *ta(G)*- can also be accompanied by a form of reduplication.

Distributive numerals with prefixation of *ta(G)*-

In this case, the prefix *ta(G)*- can be read as a form of echoed prefixes or thickening of the initial consonants in the base morpheme. This form of resonance changes to consonant / *r* / if the basic morpheme starts with vowel / *e* / and becomes / *k* / in front of vowel / *a* /. Example in Table 1.

Table 1.

<i>ta(G)</i> -	seddi 'satu'	→	tassedi 'one each'
	dua 'dua'	→	taddua 'each of two'
	tellu 'tiga'	→	tattellu 'three each'
	lima 'lima'	→	tallima 'five each'
	pitu 'tujuh'	→	tappitu 'seven each'
	seppulo 'sepuluh'	→	tassepulo 'ten each'
	eppa 'empat'	→	tareppa 'four each'
	enneng 'enam'	→	tarenneng 'each of six'
	arua 'delapan'	→	tarenneng 'each of six'
	asera 'sembilan'	→	takkasera 'nine each'

In speech there are examples:

- (1) Tattellusionrong 'Three pieces one place'
- (2) Tasseppulositunrung 'ten in one trip (banana)'
- (3) Tareppasiwali 'each of four sides on one side'

Prefix **ta(G)**-with the meaning of ownership

Distributive numerals with prefixation**ta(G)**- appear in relation to the need for possessiveness, for example:

1. Single first person ownership

Single first person ownership is stated with **-ku** suffix. Example:

- (4) tasseddikku 'each party gets one'
- (5) tappitukku 'each party gets seven'
- (6) takkaseraku 'each party gets nine'

2. The first plural ownership

Multiple first person ownership is stated by suffix **-ta**.

- (7) tassedditta 'you and I get one'
- (8) tappitutta 'you and I get seven'
- (9) takkaserata 'you and I get nine'

3. Ownership of a single second person

Ownership of a single second person is stated with **mu-** suffix

- (10) tasseddimmu 'each of you gets one'
- (11) tappitummu 'each of you gets seven'
- (12) takkaseramu 'each of you gets nine'

4. Single third person

The ownership of a single third person is expressed by the suffix **-na**.

- (13) tasseddinna 'each of them gets one'
- (14) tappitunna 'each of them gets seven'
- (15) takkaserana 'each of them gets nine'

Distributive numerals with prefixationta(G)**- accompanied by reduplication**

Distributive numerals with prefixation**ta(G)**- which is accompanied by reduplication can be given the following example.

- (16) tasseddi-seddi 'each one'
- (17) taddua-dua 'two each'
- (18) tallima-lima 'five each'
- (19) tappitu-pitu 'seven each'
- (20) Maddennektassedi-seddikalukue. 'Fall one by one the coconut'
- (21) Mabbarisiktaddua-duatentarae 'Line up two of the two armies'
- (22) Siotasseppulo-seppuloikalukue 'Tie ten by ten of the coconut'

Another example in the sentence:

- (23) Natimpaktassedi-seddinipattongkoknabeppaesibawainanre-e.
'He opens one by one the cake and rice cover'
- (24) Naiyaarungngepadanaiatamanengngianakdaraetassedi-seddi.
'As for the king, each of them has examined the girls one by one.'
- (25) Mappakkonirocaritanaanakkarungngerilalingtaceddi-ceddi pole kuarisingae.
'That's the story of the king's son who was brought one by one by the lion.'

In fact, the prefix **ta(G)**- can also be added to the category 'standby' word interrogativa and other words that contain the number of units or sizes. Example:

- (26) Tassiagatta? 'How many each?
- (27) Tassigoppota. 'Each one has a pile'
- (28) Tassiseputa. 'Each one has a bag'
- (29) Tassibakuta. 'Each gets one basket'
- (30) Tassikatoangta. 'Each one has a basin'

Behavior of the Bugis Distributive Numeral Syntax

On the other hand, distributive numerals in BL can also be formed with certain lexical elements. In this case, there are two lexical elements, namely the "each" limb and at each. Both are different, both in terms of morphological behavior and in terms of syntactic behavior. In terms of morphological behavior, the "lexeme" can experience a morphological process, which is to add the prefix to the face "each" and to be a person who is alone. In addition to this, the words can experience reduplication to be: ekek each.

Example:

- (31) Ia-naronapogautungkek-tungkekele.
'That's what is done every morning'
 - (32) Tungkek-tungkekessosinilokkanajoppa-joppa.
'Every day he always travels'
- Actually *tungkek* word can be meaningful alone, for example in the context of:
- (33) Massumpajaktungkek 'Self-serving '
 - (34) anaktungkek 'single children'
 - (35) Sippattungkekakjamai 'A person to do it '
 - (36) Mattungkek-tungkek anting-anting anakdarae. 'Every girl has earrings'
 - (37) Memmanatungke-tungketaung. 'Maternity every year'.

As distributive numerals, the form of *tungkek-tungkek*, besides being able to accompany time nouns such as examples (26) and (27), it can also accompany cardinal numerals (principal), for example:

- (38) Tungkek-tungkekduataungngemmanaksi.
'Every two years he gives birth to another child '
- (39) Tungkek-tungkeklimataungngemaccoddoksitauwe.
'Every five years people stab (choose the president)'

The words *pada* 'each' as distributive numerical lexicons cannot experience any morphological processes, but this word can appear, both in front of basic numerals and in front of verbs and adjectives. Example:

- (40) Padasedditawata. 'Each gets one quota'
- (41) Padalimarijala. 'Each gets five'
- (42) Padaduariakkatanning. 'Each holds two'
- (43) Padarialatawata. 'Each takes rations'
- (44) Padarijamajamang-jamangta. 'Each of them does his work'
- (45) Padaengkatawana. 'Each has a share or ration'
- (46) Padarionroibolata. 'Each occupies his house'
- (47) Padanasappamanengsilaoanna. 'Each one is looking for his friend'
- (48) Padalaingsifaknatauwe. 'The nature of each person is different'
- (49) Padamajaamanengsifakna. 'Each one is bad in nature.'
- (50) Padamakessingwajunna. 'Each one has nice clothes.'

IV. CONCLUSION

Based on its morphological behavior, BL distributive numerals can be formed by using the prefix **ta(G)-** on basic numerals. Prefix **ta(G)-** this can also be accompanied by a suffix that states ownership, in this case possessive **-ku** (first person singular), **-ta** (first person plural), **-mu** (second person singular), and **-na** (third person singular). In addition to this, BL distributive numerals can also be in the form of reduplication, then, based on its syntactic behavior, BL distributive numerals is explicitly expressed as every 'lexical. This word can also experience a morphological process, namely the addition of **maG-** prefixes into **mattungkek** 'each' and the **sipattungkek** 'alone'. In addition to this, the words can also experience reduplication to be: **tungkek-tungkek** 'each '. Syntactically, **tungkek** word always precede the numerical and noun word categories and cannot stand alone, while the **pada** word does not undergo a morphological process as well as a **tungkek** word and can appear, both in front of the numeral word, and in front of verbs and adjectives. All of these facts show that BL is very rich in the form or construction of distributive numerals, both based on morphological behavior and syntactic behavior. Then, sociologically, these symptoms indicate that the Buginese community has a social nature that likes to share something with other people.

REFERENCES

- [1] Abbas, Asriani, *Perilaku Morfosintaksis Verba Bahasa Makassar*, disertasi Doktor, Program Pascasarjana Universitas Hasanuddin, Makassar, Indonesia 2013.
- [2] Alwi, Hasan dkk, *Tata Bahasa Baku Bahasa Indonesia* Departemen Pendidikan dan Kebudayaan Republik Indonesia, Jakarta, 2003.
- [3] Alwasilah, A. Chaedar, *Pokoknya Kualitatif: Dasar-dasar Merancang dan Melakukan Penelitian Kualitatif*, Dunia Pustaka Jaya & Pusat Studi Sunda, Jakarta, 2003.
- [4] Ba'dulu, Abd. Muis, *Morfosintaksis*, Diklat, Program Pascasarjana UNM, Makassar, 2003.
- [5] Bloomfield, Leonardo, *Language*. Holt, Rinehart and Winston, New York, 1933.
- [6] Champollion, Lucas, *Parts of a whole: Distributivity as a bridge between aspect and measurement*, doctoral diss, University of Pennsylvania, Philadelphia, PA., 2010.
- [7] Champollion, Lucas, *Distributivity, collectivity, and cumulativity*, in Wiley's Companion to Semantics, Lisa Matthewson, Cecile Meier, Hotze Rullmann, and Thomas Ede Zimmermann (editor), 2014.
- [8] Chomsky, Noam, *Aspect of The Theory of Syntax*, MIT Press., Cambridge, 1998.
- [9] Dardjowidjojo, Soenjono, *Indonesian Syntax*, Georgetown University, Michigan, 1966.
- [10] Dardjowidjojo, Soenjono, *Beberapa Aspek Linguistik Indonesia*, Djambatan, Jakarta, 1983.
- [11] Darwis, Muhammad., *Morfologi Bahasa Indonesia: Bidang Verba*, Menara Intan, Makassar, 2012.
- [12] Darwis, Muhammad, *Perilaku Morfosintaksis Bahasa Bugis*. Prosiding Kongres Internasional Masyarakat Linguistik (KIMLI), MLI – Universitas Lampung, Bandar Lampung, 2014.
- [13] Donohue, Mark and Owen, Edwards, *Number in Tolaki* Dalam Klammer, Marian and František Kratochvíl (Editor), p. 27-42, 2014.

- [14] Hasyim, M., PrasuriKuswarini, P., Kaharuddin, Semiotic Model for Equivalence and Non-Equivalence in Translation,*Humanities & Social Sciences Reviews*, 8 (3), 2020, 381-391.
- [15] Nurahmad, Muhammad, *SubkategorisasiNumeraliaBahasaBugis: AnalisisPerilakuMorfosintaksis*, Dissertation Draft, Program PascasarjanaFakultasIlmuBudaya, UniversitasHasanuddin, Makassar, 2019.
- [16] Rawe, BesseTenri, Maknadan NilaiPappasengdalamLontara' LatoaKajaoLaliddongdenganArummppone: Analisis Hermeneutika.*JurnalIlmuBudaya*, 8 (1), 2020, 15-23.